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October 6, 2021 (v1) Dataset Open Access

Potential Cell Lysis Mechanisms for B. subtilis

Samuel Chagas; Raúl Acosta Murillo;

Description: A list of potential cell lysis mechanisms for Bacillus subtilis, cured and organized as part of the partnership between iGEM UANL and UNILA teams in the design of a Kill Switch for B. subtilis. For more information on both designs, check out the projects wikis: iGEM UNILA LatAm 2021.&

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February 12, 2022 (v1) Book Restricted Access

PROCUREMENT PT-2021

PUSPT-2021;

Course codes in this document: PUS 304, PUS 202, PUS 308, PUS 208, PUS 210, PUS 112, PUS 302, PUS 204, PUS 110, PUS 218, BPS 308, PUS 206, PUS 104

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INTERIOR DESIGN - 2021

INTDESIGN-2021;

Course codes in this document: IDT 108, IDT 102, FDP 104, IDT 304, IDT 310, IDT 306, IDT 104, IDT 106, FDP 108, FDP 110, FDP 114, AFS 111, IDT 112, COS 102,

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SEC & MGT FT-2021

SECFT-2021;

Course codes in this document: SMS 114, SMS 206, SMS 308, BSMS 404, SMS 202, SMS 116, SMS 386, SMS 208, SMS 210, PUS 202, ETP 302, COS 102, DBA 212, SMS 208, SMS 106, SMS 308, DBA 210, LAN 120, SMS 321

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List of OHEJP Publications 2021

The One Health EJP is a landmark partnership between partners across Europe, aligning and integrating medical, veterinary and environmental scientific communities to address potential and existing risks that originate at the animal-human-environmental interface.

All our project outcomes from the 5 year programme are available to view in yearly publication lists and via our [website](#).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 773830

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The SARS-CoV-2 Reproduction Number R_0 in Cats.

Gonzales, J. L., de Jong, M., Gerhards, N. M., & Van der Poel, W. (2021). *Viruses*, 13(12), 2480.

Project: **COVRIN**

An FSKX compliant source attribution model for salmonellosis and a look at its major hidden pitfalls.

Sundermann, E. M., Correia Carreira, G., Käsbohrer, A. (2021). *Food Modelling Journal*, 2, e70008.

Project: **MATRIX**

Genomic Epidemiology and Strain Taxonomy of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*.

Guglielmini, J., Hennart, M., Badell, E., Toubiana, J., Criscuolo, A., & Brisse, S. (2021). *Journal of clinical microbiology*, 59 (12), e0158121.

Project: **Codes4strains**

Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on human salmonellosis in the Netherlands.

Mughini-Gras, L., Chanamé Pinedo, L., Pijnacker, R., Van den Beld, M., Wit, B., Veldman, K., Bosch, T., Franz, E. (2021). *Epidemiology and Infection*, 149, E254.

Project: **ADONIS**

Impact of animal saliva on the performance of rapid antigen tests for detection of SARS-CoV-2 (wildtype and variants B.1.1.7 and B.1.351).

Hagag, I. T., Weber, S., Sadeghi, B., Groschup, M. H., & Keller, M. (2021). *Veterinary microbiology*, 262, 109243.

Project: **COVRIN**

Characterization of Clinical *Escherichia coli* Strains Producing a Novel Shiga Toxin 2 Subtype in Sweden and Denmark.

Bai, X., Scheutz, F., Dahlgren, H. M., Hedenström, I., & Jernberg, C. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9(11), 2374.

Project: **OH-HARMONY-CAP**

Coverage of the national surveillance system for human *Salmonella* infections, Belgium, 2016-2020.

Van Goethem N., Van Den Bossche A., Ceyskens P. J., Lajot A., Coucke W., Vernelen K., Roosens N. H. C., De Keersmaecker S. C. J., Van Caueren D., Mattheus W. (2021) *PLoS ONE*, 16(8): e0256820.

Project: **ADONIS**

Myocardial Injury Complicated by Systolic Dysfunction in a COVID-19-Positive Dog.

Romito G., Bertaglia T., Bertaglia L., Decaro N., Uva A., Rugna G., Moreno A., Vincifori G., Dondi F., Diana A., Cipone M. (2021) *Animals*, 11(12):3506.

Project: **COVRIN**

Long-term persistence of neutralizing SARS-CoV-2 antibodies in pets.

Decaro, N., Grassi, A., Lorusso, E., Patterson, E. I., Lorusso, A., Desario, C., Anderson, E. R., Vasinioti, V., Wastika, C. E., Hughes, G. L., Valleriani, F., Colitti, B., Ricci, D., Buonavoglia, D., Rosati, S., Cavaliere, N., Paltrinieri, S., Lauzi, S., Elia, G., & Buonavoglia, C. (2021). *Transboundary and emerging diseases*, 10.1111/tbed.14308. Advance online publication.

Project: **COVRIN**

Identification of Oocyst-Driven *Toxoplasma gondii* Infections in Humans and Animals through Stage-Specific Serology—Current Status and Future Perspectives.

Álvarez García G., Davidson R., Jokelainen P., Klevar S., Spano F., Seeber F. (2021) *Microorganisms*, 9(11):2346.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Differential susceptibility of SARS-CoV-2 in animals: Evidence of ACE2 host receptor distribution in companion animals, livestock and wildlife by immunohistochemical characterisation.

Lean F.Z.X., Núñez A., Spiro S., Priestnall S.L., Vreman S., Bailey D., James J., Wrigglesworth E., Suarez-Bonnet A., Conceicao C., Thakur N., Byrne A.M.P., Ackroyd S., Delahay R. J., van der Poel W. H. M., Brown I.H., Fooks A.R., Brookes S.M. (2021). *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 1–12.

Project: **COVRIN**

Changes in serum biomarkers of inflammation in bovine besnoitiosis.

González-Barrio, D., Huertas-López, A., Diezma-Díaz, C., Ferre I., Cerón J. J., Ortega-Mora L. M., Álvarez-García G. (2021) *Parasites Vectors*, 14, 488.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Identification of molecular biomarkers associated with disease progression in the testis of bulls infected with *Besnoitia besnoiti*.

González-Barrio D., Diezma-Díaz C., Gutiérrez-Expósito D., Tabanera E., Jiménez-Meléndez A., Pizarro M., González-Huecas M., Ferre I., Ortega-Mora L. M., Álvarez-García G. (2021) *Vet Res*, 52,106.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Molecular survey of *Besnoitia* spp. (Apicomplexa) in faeces from European wild mesocarnivores in Spain.

González-Barrio D., Köster P.C., Habela M.A., Martín-Pérez M., Fernández-García J.L., Balseiro A., Barral M., Nájera F., Figueiredo A.M., Palacios M.J., Mateo M., Carmena D., Álvarez-García G., Calero-Bernal R. (2021). *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 68, 3156– 3166.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Seroprevalence of *Toxoplasma gondii* in outdoor dogs and cats in Bangkok, Thailand.

Huertas-López A., Sukhumavasi W., Álvarez-García G., Martínez-Subiela S., Cano-Terriza D., Almería S., Dubey J.P., García-Bocanegra I., Cerón J.J., Martínez-Carrasco C. (2021). *Parasitology*, 148(7), 843-849. DOI: 10.1017/S0031182021000421

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Development and validation of a time-resolved fluorescence immunoassay for the detection of anti-*Toxoplasma gondii* antibodies in goats.

Huertas-López A., Martínez-Subiela S., Cerón J.J., Vázquez-Calvo Á., Pazmiño-Bonilla E.D., López-Ureña N.M., Martínez-Carrasco C., Álvarez-García G. (2021) *Veterinary Parasitology*, 293, 109432.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Draft Genome Sequence of a Multidrug-Resistant *Escherichia coli* Sequence Type 1193 Pandemic Clone Isolated from Wastewater in Austria

Cabal A., Peischl N., Rab G., Stöger A., Springer B., Sucher J., Allerberger F. and Ruppitsch W. (2021) *Microbiol Resour Announc*, 10:e00762-21.

Project: **FED-AMR**

Risk-based control of *Campylobacter* spp. in broiler farms and slaughtered flocks to mitigate risk of human campylobacteriosis – A One Health approach.

Foddai A., Nauta M. and Ellis-Iversen J. (2021) *Microbial Risk Analysis*, 100190, ISSN 2352-3522.

Project: **ORION**

A large panel of chicken cells are invaded *in vivo* by *Salmonella* Typhimurium even when depleted of all known invasion factors.

Roche S. M., Holbert S., Le Vern Y., Rossignol C., Rossignol A., Velge P. and Virlogeux-Payant I. (2021) *Open Biology*, 11, 210117

Project: **MoMIR-PPC**

Large diversity of linezolid-resistant isolates discovered in food-producing animals through linezolid selective monitoring in Belgium in 2019.

Timmermans M, Bogaerts B, Vanneste K, De Keersmaecker S C J, Roosens N H C, Kowalewicz C, Simon G, Argudín M A, Deplano A, Hallin M, Wattiau P, Fretin D, Denis O and Boland C. (2021) *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, dkab376.

Project: **LIN-RES**

SARS-CoV-2 surveillance in Italy through phylogenomic inferences based on Hamming distances derived from pan-SNPs, -MNPs and -InDels.

Di Pasquale A, Radomski N, Mangone I, Calistri P, Lorusso A and Cammà C. (2021). *BMC Genomics*, 22, 782.

Project: **COVRIN**

Morphological Characteristics of Alveolar and Cystic Echinococcosis Lesions in Human Liver and Bone.

Barth, TFE, Casulli, A (2021). *Pathogens*, 10, 1326.

Project: **MEME**

Peek into the Plasmidome of Global Sewage.

Kirstahler, P., Teudt, F., Otani, S., Aarestrup, FM, Pamp, SJ., (2021). *mSystems*, 6:e00283-21.

Project: **FULL-FORCE**

The disease burden of ocular toxoplasmosis in Denmark in 2019: Estimates based on laboratory testing of ocular samples and on publicly available register data.

Marstrand, J., Kurtzhals, JAL., Fuchs, HJ., Nielsen, HV., Jokelainen, P. (2021). *Parasite Epidemiology and Control*, 15, e00229.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance dynamics of *Escherichia coli* in wastewater and river environments.

Delgado-Blas, JF., Ovejero, CM., David, S., Montero, N., Calero-Caceres, W., Garcillan-Barcia, MP., de la Cruz, F., Muniesa, M., Aanensen, DM., Gonzalez-Zorn, B. (2021). *Communications Biology*, 4, 457.

Project: **WORLDCOM**

The cytotoxic potential of *Bacillus cereus* strains of various origins.

Glasset, B., Sperry, M., Dervyn, R., Herbin, S., Brisabois, A., Ramarao, N. (2021). *Food Microbiology*, 98, 103759.

Project: **TOX-detect**

A longitudinal study of *Toxoplasma gondii* seroconversion on four large Danish sow farms.

Olsen, A., Denwood, M., Houe, H., Birk Jensen, T., Nielsen, HV. (2021). *Veterinary Parasitology*, 295, 109460.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Zoonotic pathogens in wild muskoxen (*Ovibos moschatus*) and domestic sheep (*Ovis aries*) from Greenland.

Berg, RPKD., Stensvold, CR., Jokelainen, P., Grønlund, AK., Nielsen, HV., Kutz, S., Kapel CMO. (2021). *Veterinary Medicine and Science*, 1-14.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Comparison of Direct and Indirect *Toxoplasma gondii* Detection and Genotyping in Game: Relationship and Challenges.

Stollberg, K.C., Schares, G., Mayer-Scholl, A., Hrushetska, I., Diescher, S., Johne, A., Richter, M.H., Bier, N.S. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9, 1663.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Attention to the Tripartite's one health measures in national action plans on antimicrobial resistance.

Munkholm, L., Rubin, O., Bækkeskov, E., & Humboldt-Dachroeden, S. (2021). *Journal of public health policy*, 42(2), 236–248.

Project: **SUSTAIN**

Draft genome sequences of two *Listeria monocytogenes* strains isolated from invasive snails (*Arion vulgaris*) in Austria in 2019.

Pietzka, A., Murer, A., Lennkh, A., Hauser, K., Vötsch, K., Springer, B., Allerberger, F., Ruppitsch, W. (2021). *Microbiology Resource Announcements*, 10:e00375-21.

Project: **LISTADAPT**

Refinement of the COHESIVE Information System towards a unified ontology of food terms for the public health organisations.

Mangone, I., Radomski, N., Di Pasquale, A., Santurbano, A., Calistri, P., Cammà, C., Maassen, K. (2021).

Project: **COHESIVE**

Mining Public Metagenomes for Environmental Surveillance of Parasites: A Proof of Principle.

Franssen F., Janse I., Janssen D., Caccio SM., Vatta P., van der Giessen J., van Passel MWJ. (2021). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 12:622356.

Project: **PARADISE**

A shotgun metagenomics approach to detect and characterise unauthorised genetically modified microorganisms in microbial fermentation products.

Buytaers, F E., Fraiture, M-A., Berbers, B., Vandermassen, E., Hoffman, S., Papazova, N., Vanneste, K., Marchal, K., Roosens, N H C., De Keersmaecker, S C J. (2021). *Food Chemistry: Molecular Sciences*, 2, 100023.

Project: **FARMED**

A user-friendly decision support tool to assist one-health risk assessors.

Dewar, R., Gavin, C., McCarthy, C., Taylor, R A., Cook, C., Simons, R R L. (2021). *One Health*, 13, 100266.

Project: **COHESIVE**

Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study.

Badell, E., Alharazi, A., Criscuolo, A., Almoayed, K., Lefrancq, N., Bouchez, V., Guglielmini, J., Hennart, M., Carmi-Leroy, A., Zidane, N., Pascal-Perrigault, M., Lebreton, M., Martini, H., Salje, H., Toubiana, J., Dureab, F., Dhabaan, G., & Brisse, S., Rawah, A. & Al-Somainy, A. (2021) *The Lancet Microbe*, 2(8), E386-E396.

Project: **Codes4strains**

The Glossaryfication Web Service: an automated glossary creation tool to support the One Health community.

Scaccia, N., Günther, T., Lopez de Abechuco, E., Filter, M. (2021). *Research Ideas and Outcomes*, 7: e70183.

Project: **ORION**

Monitoring of Antimicrobial Resistance to Aminoglycosides and Macrolides in *Campylobacter coli* and *Campylobacter jejuni* From Healthy Livestock in Spain (2002–2018).

Lopez-Chavarrias, V., Ugarte-Ruiz, M., Barcena, C., Olarra, A., Garcia, M., Saez, J.L., de Frutos, C., Serrano, T., Perez, I., Moreno, M.A., Dominguez, L., Alvarez, J. (2021). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 12:689262.

Project: **DISCOVER**

One Health practices across key agencies in Sweden – Uncovering barriers to cooperation, communication and coordination.

Humboldt-Dachroeden, S. (2021). *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*, pp 1-7.

Project: **SUSTAIN**

Clinically Relevant *Escherichia coli* Isolates from Process Waters and Wastewater of Poultry and Pig Slaughterhouses in Germany.

Savin, M., Bierbaum, G., Kreyenschmidt, J., Sib, E., Schmoger, S., Käsbohrer, A., Hammerl, J.-A. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9, 698.

Projects: **ARDIG** and **FULL- FORCE**

Outcome of Different Sequencing and Assembly Approaches on the Detection of Plasmids and Localization of Antimicrobial Resistance Genes in Commensal *Escherichia coli*.

Juraschek, K., Borowiak, M., Tausch, S.H., Malorny, B., Käsbohrer, A., Otani, S., Schwarz, S., Meemken, D., Deneke, C., Hammerl, J.A. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9, 598.

Projects: **ARDIG** and **FULL- FORCE**

A ready-to-use dose-response model of *Campylobacter jejuni* implemented in the FSKX-standard.

Sundermann, E.M., Nauta, M., Swart, A. (2021). *Food Modelling Journal* 2, e63309.

Project: **MATRIX**

Parasitic Intestinal Protists of Zoonotic Relevance Detected in Pigs by Metabarcoding and Real-Time PCR.

Stensvold, C.R., Jirků-Pomajbíková, K., Tams, K.W., Jokelainen, P., Berg, R.P.K.D., Marving, E., Petersen, R., Randi, F., Andersen, L., O'Brien, A., Angen, Ø., Nielsen, H.V. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9, 1189.

Project: **PARADISE**

Isolation Procedure for CP *E. coli* from Caeca Samples under Review towards an Increased Sensitivity.

Pauly, N., Klaar, Y., Skladnikiewicz-Ziemer, T., Juraschek, K., Grobbel, M., Hammerl, J.A., Hemmers, L., Käsbohrer, A., Schwarz, S., Meemken, D., Tenhagen, B.-A., Irrgang, A. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9, 1105.

Project: **IMPART**

A one health glossary to support communication and information exchange between the human health, animal health and food safety sectors.

Buschhardt, T., Günther, T., Taras, S., Skjerdal, T., Torpdahl, M., Gethmann, J., Filippitzi, M., Maria-Eleni, M., Maassen, C., Catharina, J., Jore, S., Solveig, E., Ellis-Iversen, J., Johanne. (2021). *One Health*, 13.

Projects: **ORION** and **COHESIVE**

Effect of Biscuit Flour and Fermented Defatted “Alperujo” Co-Administration on Intestinal Mucosa Morphology and Productive Performance in Laying Hens.

Porrás, N., Rebolledo-Merino, A., Barcena, C., Mayoral-Alegre, F.J., Lomillos, J.M., Domínguez, L., Rodríguez-Bertos, A. (2021). *Animals*, 11, 1075.

Project: **MoMIR**

New global targets for NTDs in the WHO roadmap 2021–2030.

Casulli, A. (2021). *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 15(5):e0009373.

Project: **MeME**

One Health Surveillance Codex: promoting the adoption of One Health solutions within and across European countries.

Filter, Matthias., Buschhardt, Tasia., Dórea, Fernanda., Lopez de Abechucó, Estibaliz., Günther, Taras., Sundermann, Esther M.; Gethmann, Jörn., Dups-Bergmann, Johanna., Lagesen, Karin., Ellis-Iversen, Johanne. (2021). *One Health*, 12.

Project: **ORION**

Assessing Environmental Factors within the One Health Approach.

Humboldt-Dachroeden, S., Mantovani, A. (2021). *Medicina*, 57(3), 240.

Project: **SUSTAIN (PhD)**

Molecular analysis suggests that Namibian cheetahs (*Acinonyx jubatus*) are definitive hosts of a so far undescribed *Besnoitia* species.

Schares, G., Joeres, M., Rachel, F., Tuschy, M., Czirják, GÁ., Maksimov, P., Conraths, FJ., Wachter, B. (2021). *Parasites and Vectors*, 14, 201.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Expanding the Known Repertoire of C-Type Lectin Receptors Binding to *Toxoplasma gondii* Oocysts Using a Modified High-Resolution Immunofluorescence Assay.

Fabian, B. T., Lepenies, B., Schares, G., Dubey, J. P., Spano, F., Seeber, F. (2021). *mSphere*, 6:e01341-20.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Infection prevention and control practices of ambulatory veterinarians: A questionnaire study in Finland.

Verkola, M., Järvelä, T., Järvinen, A., Jokelainen, P., Virtala, A.-M., Kinnunen, P. M., Heikinheimo, A. (2021). *Veterinary Medicine and Science*, p1-12.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Experimental Infection with *Toxoplasma gondii* in Broiler Chickens (*Gallus Domesticus*): Seroconversion, Tissue Cyst Distribution, and Prophylaxis.

Nedişan, M. E., Györke, A., Ştefănuţ, C. L., Kalmár, Z., Friss, Z., Blaga, R., Blaizot, A., Toma-Naic, A., Mircean, V.; Schares, G., Djurković-Djaković, O., Klun, I., Villena, I., Cozma, V. (2021). *Parasitology Research*, 120, pp 593- 603.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

A real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction for the specific detection of *Hammondia hammondi* and its differentiation from *Toxoplasma gondii*.

Schares, G., Globokar Vrhovec, M., Tuschy, M., Joeres, M., Bärwald, A., Koudela, B., Dubey, J. P., Maksimov, P., Conraths, F. J. (2021). *Parasites and Vectors*, 15, 74. 1-8

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Molecular Methods for the Detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* Oocysts in Fresh Produce: An Extensive Review.

Slana, I., Bier, N., Bartosova, B., Marucci, G., Possenti, P., Mayer-Scholl, A., Jokelainen, P., Lalle, M. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9 (1), 167.

Project: **TOXOSOURCES**

Exposure to Quaternary Ammonium Compounds Selects Resistance to Ciprofloxacin in *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Guérin, A., Bridier, A., Le Grandois, P., Sévellec, Y., Palma, F., Félix, B., Roussel, S., Soumet, C. (2021). *Pathogens*, 10, 220.

Project: **LISTADAPT**

Detection of Norovirus Variant GII.4 Hong Kong in Asia and Europe, 2017-2019.

Chi-Wai Chan, M., Roy, S., Bonifacio, J., Zhang, YY., Chhabra, P., Chan, JCM., Celma, C., Igoy, MA., Lau SL., Mohammad, KN., Vinjé, J., Vennema, H., Breuer, J., Koopmans, M., de Graaf, M. (2021). *Emerging Infectious Diseases*, 27(1), pp 283- 293.

Project: **METASTAVA**

Identification of *Echinococcus granulosus* Genotypes G1 and G3 by SNPs Genotyping Assays.

Bonelli, P., Dei Giudici, S., Peruzzu, A., Mura, L., Santucciu, C., Maestrone, C., Masala, G. (2021). *Pathogens*, 10, 125.

Project: **MEME**

COVID-19 in health-care workers in three hospitals in the south of the Netherlands: a cross-sectional study.

Sikkema, RS., Pas, SD., Nieuwenhuijse, DF., O'Toole, A., Verweij, JJ., van der Linden, A., Chestakova, I., Schapendonk, C., Pronk, M., Lexmond, P., Bestebroer, T., Overmars, RJ., van Nieuwkoop, S., van den Bijllaardt, W., Bentvelsen RG., van Rijen, MML., Buiting, AGM., van Oudheusden, AJG., Diederens, BM., Bergmans, AMC., van der Eijk, A., Molenkamp, R., Rambaut, A., Timen, A., Kluytmans, JAJW., Oude Munnink, BB., Kluytmans van den Bergh, MFQ., Koopmans, MPG. (2021). *The Lancet: Infectious Disease*, 20(11), p1273-1280

Project: **METASTAVA**

Co-occurrence of the blaVIM-1 and blaSHV-12 genes on an IncHI2 plasmid of an *Escherichia coli* isolate recovered from German livestock.

Pauly, N., Hammerl, JA., Schwarz, S., Grobbel, M., Meemken, D., Malorny, B., Tenhagen, BA., Käsbohrer, A., Irrgang, A. (2020). *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, 76(2), 531–533.

Project: **IMPART**

Molecular Characterisation of *Giardia duodenalis* in Children and Adults Sampled in Algeria.

Belkessa, S., Thomas-Lopez, D., Houali, K., Ghalmi, F., Stensvold, C R. (2021). *Microorganisms*, 9 (1), 54.

Project: **PARADISE**

All OHEJP Publications from the 5 year programme can be viewed at: onehealthjep.eu

